

Cyberloafing, Current Development and Future Research: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

Background: The increasing digitalisation of the workplace has further intensified scholarly interest in Cyberloafing, defined as the use of non-work-related electronic devices at work, which has become a growing concern. However, the existing literature is fragmented and requires consolidation to provide a comprehensive and contemporary overview of cyberloafing research while mapping its intellectual boundaries.

Objectives: This paper aims to address the gap by conducting a systematic literature review on cyberloafing, also known as cyberslacking, in the workplace.

Methodology: This systematic review, conducted using the PRISMA protocol, examines 73 articles to identify key actors, theoretical frameworks employed, and methodological trends in the field's established aspects. The data were gathered from eligible articles published in Tier 1 journals between 2015 and 2022. Keywords used in the selection process included *cyberloafing*, *personal web usage*, *cyberslacking*, and *work deviance*.

Result: This review highlights key gaps in cyberloafing research, emphasising the need for more qualitative studies to explore individual experiences, motivations, and cultural perceptions beyond

the dominant regions, as well as for broader theoretical frameworks beyond the commonly used Theory of Planned Behaviour.

Conclusion: While cyberloafing research has evolved through different stages, it remains an emerging and challenging field due to the many evolving issues surrounding it.

Unique Contribution: This literature study is unique because it employs two approaches: the PRISMA method and Watase, an analysis system developed by lecturers that is combined to provide a detailed examination of the literature. This unique methodological approach and meta-analytic insights help move the cyberloafing discourse forward.

Key Recommendation: Future studies could explore alternative theoretical frameworks to provide deeper insights into the phenomenon. Additionally, this study is primarily focused on theoretical findings and does not extensively address practical implications.

Keywords: Cyberloafing, Systematic Literature Review, Organisation

Introduction

Currently, we live in an environment dominated by artificial intelligence, which has significantly simplified our lives. The internet-connected AI has a profound impact on all aspects of our lives, both positively and negatively. The Internet at work also creates new opportunities for employees to engage in non-work-related and sometimes unproductive activities. (Huma et al., 2017). Based on a study by Jandaghi et al. (2015), the widespread use of social media by employees results in lost productivity and increased leaks of sensitive information, defamation, and misinformation.

Initially, academics and scholars needed to be more concerned with the term or concept of cyberloafing. It was not until the 1990s that the idea of "cyberloafing" was first proposed, and it is now recognised as a form of workplace and asset deviance. (Wu et al., 2020). Companies worldwide gradually increased their investment in Internet resources in the early 2000s. As technology expands within the enterprise, so does the potential for exploitation.

The definition of cyberloafing is the use of non-work-related electronic devices at work (Lim, 2002). Employees are estimated to spend up to two hours at work each day cyberloafing, costing companies up to \$85 billion annually (Zakrzewski, 2016). Lim (2002) originally defined *cyberloafing* as an employee's voluntary use of an organisation's Internet access for non-work purposes during work hours. Several research studies related to cyberloafing have explored why people engage in cyberloafing, the mechanisms underlying it, and its impact on work (Hensel & Kacprzak, 2020).

Cyberloafing is still considered a phenomenon that adversely affects efficiency and productivity, as it involves using the Internet during working hours for personal gain. (Pindek et al., 2018) Furthermore, research on cyberloafing is necessary for applied sciences such as management because organisations' dependence on the use of the Internet in the workplace is increasing and will continue to increase in the future. Mihelič et al. (2023) say that subjective norms are negatively related to cyberloafing in the classroom, while moral disengagement is positively correlated.

Lim and Teo (2024) conducted a literature review on the causes and consequences of cyberloafing, including both its good and negative impacts. Additionally, they examined the relevance of

company policies in addressing this issue. In our literature review, we specifically examined variables related to cyberloafing. We analysed journals that mentioned cyberloafing, including the methodology employed, research settings, and the nations from which the cyberloafing researchers originated.

Methodology

This section describes the strategies used in the research process and data retrieval. In conducting LSR studies, this study employs the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) approach. The literature search was conducted using the Web of Science System, which facilitates the identification, selection, and reporting of the literature search process.

PRISMA 2020 | CYBERLOAFING

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram template for systematic reviews.

The selection of databases in this systematic literature review was strategically guided by the aim of ensuring academic rigour, relevance, and credibility. Accordingly, sources were drawn exclusively from peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus Quartiles 1 to 3 (Q1-Q3). This decision replicates a commitment to methodological transparency and quality assurance. These characteristics serve as critical indicators of scholarly integrity and reliability, particularly within the interdisciplinary field of cyberloafing, which intersects organisational behaviour, human resource management, and information systems.

Result and Discussion

The findings of this literature study are generated from the preparation of the study, which summarises publications from top-tier journals. Articles in top-tier journals often address cutting-edge issues and make substantial contributions to the field. This ensures that the literature review captures the most influential and widely recognised studies on cyberloafing. The discussion opens with an overview of existing cyberloafing research, particularly studies that examine commonly explored variables, and proceeds to analyse academic journals that have featured publications on the subject. The debate proceeded by examining commonly employed methodologies in cyberloafing research, as well as the prominent ideas utilised as overarching frameworks in studies about cyberloafing. This article examines the extensive study topics within the field of cyberloafing research. Subsequently, the text proceeds to examine the countries of origin of the researchers, starting with those that have the highest number of individuals who have conducted studies on cyberloafing and gradually moving down to those with a smaller representation. (Wahyudi, 2025).

The Researched Variables on Cyberloafing

Cyberloafing has been associated with various variables from multiple background studies and perspectives, including performance, gender, creativity, job burnout, motivation, job embeddedness, emotional exhaustion, and leadership. Several previous studies have shown cyberloafing as a dependent variable. (Durak, 2020) as well as an independent variable (Wu et al., 2020)

Table 1 presents an overview of the significance and influence of these variables on cyberloafing, as well as the influence of cyberloafing on these variables. For example, when gender is associated with cyberloafing in the context of university students, the results are not significant, but some offer the significance of both. (Akbulut et al., 2017)The various research results present an exciting opportunity for researchers further to study cyberloafing in relation to several other variables.

Table 1. Variables Used in Cyberloafing Research

No	Variable	Researchers	Object	Country	Significance
1.	Gender → Cyberloafing	(Durak, 2020)	University students	Turkey	No
		(Saritepeci, 2020)	High school students	Turkey	No
		(Akbulut et al., 2017)	Students and Jobholders	Turkey	Yes

2.	Perceived Overqualification → Cyberloafing	(Andel et al., 2022)	Administrative employees	Europe	Yes
3.	Abusive supervision → Cyberloafing	(Koay et al., 2022) (Agarwal & Avey, 2020)	Public listed company Manager	Malaysia India	Yes Yes
4.	Motivation → Cyberloafing	(Elrehail et al., 2021) (Hensel & Kacprzak, 2020)	University Employee Public Administration Employee	Pakistan Poland	Yes No
5.	Job Embeddedness → Cyberloafing	(Fakoor Saghih & Nosrati, 2021)	University Employee	Iran	Yes
6.	Workplace Ostracism → Cyberloafing	(Koay, 2018)	full-time employees	United States	Yes
7.	Job Stress → Cyberloafing	(Elrehail et al., 2021)	University Employee	Pakistan	Yes
8.	Emotional Stability → Cyberloafing	(Durak, 2020)	Teacher	Turkey	No
10.	Emotional Exhaustion → Cyberloafing	(Koay, 2018)	full-time employees	United States	Yes
11.	Work engagement → Cyberloafing	(Elrehail et al., 2021) (Oosthuizen et al., 2018)	University Employee Retail and Manufacturing industry	Pakistan South Africa	Yes Yes
13.	Cyberloafing → Smartphone Addiction	(Gökçearsan et al., 2018)	undergraduate students	Turkey	Yes
14.	Cyberloafing → Psychological Detachment	(Wu et al., 2020)	Workers	China	Yes

Table 1 above illustrates several variables associated with cyberloafing and the countries where these studies were conducted. From 2015 to 2016, some research connected conscientiousness, emotional stability, and gender with cyberloafing. Subsequently, from 2017 to 2022, several variables related to cyberloafing have been studied, including conscientiousness, emotional stability, workplace ostracism, and emotional exhaustion. Several recent variables have emerged, including job stress, perceived overqualification, abusive supervision, motivation, job embeddedness, cyberloafing intention, and social cyberloafing. Based on the table, it is evident

that research on cyberloafing is predominantly conducted in countries such as Turkey and China. It is less common in European countries, the United States, and Korea. While in Asia, based on a review of articles in top-tier journals, research from Malaysia and Pakistan is more active in studying cyberloafing compared to that from Poland.

When focusing on research subjects, most articles indicate that cyberloafing is primarily studied in the context of business employees and students. Based on the overview in the table, there remains an opportunity for researchers to further investigate cyberloafing by exploring relationships involving new variables that have not been extensively studied or are still relatively rare. A key aspect of this figure is the prevalence of instructors and lecturers engaging in cyberloafing. While instructors typically face challenges in finding time for cyberloafing, they may engage in this behaviour when given the chance, driven by certain motivations.

Publication Trends of Cyberloafing Research in High-Ranked Journals

Based on a search of articles in Tier journals, several topics related to cyberloafing have been published in various journals, indicating a growing number of articles over time. The highest number of citations (519 citations) is in the *Computers in Human Behaviour* journal, indexed as a high-quality journal (Q1 ranking by Scimago, A and B rating by JOURQUAL3, impact factor \geq three by Clarivate Analytics on average, with ten articles or 14% (a summary of several years). The second highest was in the *Internet Research* journal, i.e., 112 citations with six articles or 8.1%. Furthermore, articles related to cyberloafing have been published in several journals with a broad scope, including technology, psychology, business and management, organisation, and networking journals, as well as those related to company management information systems (Table 2).

Table 2. Frequency distribution of articles by journals

Journals	Period			N	(%)
	2014 - 2016	2017- 2019	2020 - 2022		
Computers in Human Behaviour	6	3	1	10	14%
Behaviour & Information Technology	1	3	2	6	8.1%
Internet Research		3	3	6	8.1%
Current Psychology			3	3	4%
Education and Information Technologies		1	1	2	2.6%
Cognition, Technology & Work		1	1	2	2.6%
Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies		2		2	2.6%
Cyberpsychology, Behaviour, and Social Networking		2		2	2.6%
Journal of Economic Behaviour & Organization	1	1		2	2.7%
Personnel Review		1	1	2	2.7%
Perspectives in Psychiatric Care			2	2	2.7%
Journal of Management Information Systems		2		2	2.7%
Information & Management	1		1	2	2.7%
Journal of Business Ethics		2		2	2.7%

Other Journals (N=1)	2	12	14	28	39.2%
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Along with a broad scope of cyberloafing research ranging from academics to health, education, business, and accounting perspectives, as well as from nursing, psychology, and business, this indicator suggests that cyberloafing is a widespread behaviour that may be engaged in across various professional domains with internet connectivity.

Theoretical Foundations in Cyberloafing Research

Of the 72 reviewed articles, this study identified 85 theories used by 64 articles, whereas 21 do not state any theories. The number of theories surpasses the number of articles because one article may use more than one theory. The three most extensively used theories are the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Conservation of Resources Theory (COR), and Theory of Interpersonal Behaviour (TIB), each with a percentage of 21.2% (18), 15.3% (13), and 4.7%, respectively. The variety of theories used as a reference is due to the topic of cyberloafing being studied in various scientific backgrounds. This result aligns with the literature study by Lim and Teo (. This review covers the Theories in Cyberloafing Studies, including significant theories such as the Theory of Reasoned Action, the Theory of Planned Behaviour, the Theory of Interpersonal Behaviour, the Theory of Organisational Justice, and the General Deterrence Model.

Table 3. The most used theories in cyberloafing research

Theory	Period				N	(%)
	<2015	2015-2017	2018-2020	2021-2022		
Theory of Planned Behaviour	1	4	12	1	18	21.20%
Conservation of Resources Theory (COR)	0	1	8	4	13	15.30%
Theory of Interpersonal Behaviour	0	2	2	0	4	4.70%
Social Learning Theory	0	1	1	1	3	3.50%
Trait Activation Theory	0	2	0	0	2	2.40%
Boundary theory and SET Theory	0	0	2	0	2	2.40%
Affective Events Theory	0	0	1	1	2	2.40%
Work/family border theory	0	0	2	0	2	2.40%
Other Theory (N=1)	1	4	10	3	18	22%
Not stated	0	7	10	4	21	25%

Table 3 states that the theory of planned behaviour was commonly used from the first period (<2015) to the third period (2021-2022). From previous research in 2015, the theory of planned behaviour has been used primarily to explain interpersonal communication, in which people transform communication (role messages, role constraints, etc.) into their roles (rights, requirements, norms, expectations, etc.), which was assumed to be understood and learn and sent by role set members (Kahn et al., 1964). Therefore, this theory is widely used in studies of business environments (Hensel & Kacprzak, 2020). However, it is rarely used as a reference in research on educational settings (Demirtepe-Saygılı & Metin-Orta, 2021). Ajzen (1991) proposed the Planned Behaviour Theory (TPB). In this theory, an individual's intentions are the best predictor of their actions. Intentions, in turn, are predicted by a person's subjective norms and attitudes about behaviour.

The other recognised theories are generally used depending on the context of the study. For example, cyberloafing studied from a psychological perspective usually uses the Conservation of Resources Theory (Agarwal & Avey, 2020). The theory is used to find the relationship between cyberloafing and human behaviour, for example, from the opposing side (work stress) or the positive effect (happiness).

Comparison and Contrast between Different Studies

This review highlights some similarities and variations in cyberloafing research. As for quantitative methods, which are common in this topic, others use a qualitative method to explore the meaning of cyberloafing more deeply. Some studies focus on individual traits like conscientiousness and emotional stability, while others determine organisational elements such as workplace ostracism and abusive supervision. This wide range of variables underscores the complex nature of cyberloafing and the different viewpoints researchers bring to their study. Other differences are geographical and contextual when comparing the studies. Many studies come from Turkey and China, but few are from European countries and the United States. This geographical viewpoint may impact the generalisation of findings across cultures. Furthermore, while most studies continue to focus on business employees and students, many explore other contexts, such as public universities, banks, and millennials. These contextual differences underscore the broad nature of cyberloafing across various sectors and demographics, highlighting potential research gaps.

Identifying Gaps and Opportunities for Further Research

This systematic literature review reveals several key areas where further research on cyberloafing is needed to advance our understanding of this complex phenomenon. First, while quantitative studies dominate existing literature, there is a clear opportunity for more *qualitative* investigations to delve deeper into the *lived experiences* and *underlying motivations* of individuals who engage in cyberloafing. Qualitative approaches could explore how employees perceive cyberloafing, the rationales they use to justify their behaviour, and the emotional and social dynamics that influence their decisions. As the current study indicates, most articles imply that research on cyberloafing is based in Turkey and China. An opportunity exists to compare these regions with areas that have less research available and investigate the differences in perceptions, particularly given the cultural differences and beliefs.

Second, belief in specific theoretical frameworks, particularly the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), limits the scope of current cyberloafing research. Future studies could benefit from exploring alternative theoretical lenses, such as the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) or the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, to provide fresh insights into the individual and organisational factors that drive cyberloafing. For example, SCT could be used to examine the role of observational learning and self-efficacy in shaping cyberloafing behaviours. In contrast, the JD-R model could be used to explore the interplay between job demands, resources, and cyberloafing as a coping mechanism. This research reveals that public universities, businesses, banks, students, and the millennial generation are among the topics covered. While the current research has a specific focus, there is an opportunity to explore why research is lacking in areas outside universities, businesses, banks, and among students and the millennial generation. What are the

nuances of the digital world in these settings? Are those settings less likely to leverage digital tools, or is it simply an area where limited research has been conducted? By addressing these gaps, future researchers can contribute to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of cyberloafing and its implications for individuals and organisations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have provided a comprehensive review of current research in cyberloafing. Due to several research gaps, cyberloafing is still a fascinating subject. Based on this literature analysis, some Asian nations have only recently begun examining cyberloafing; therefore, additional variables may emerge upon further investigation. Additionally, current academics are concerned about the effects of cyberloafing on various generations of workers, given its impact on productivity. Furthermore, the work culture in multiple firms will be an intriguing subject to explore in more depth.

From the previous description, it is noticeable that study trends concerning cyberloafing are interconnected with technology, education, and industry. Nevertheless, there is still the possibility of investigating cyberloafing from alternative viewpoints. Additionally, we can explore cyberloafing from many underexplored perspectives, such as workplace deviance or self-efficacy. The purpose of this mapping is to offer research guidance and facilitate an in-depth investigation into cyberloafing by utilising referenced methods and theories.

Moreover, from a methodological perspective, one can explore deeper into the utilisation of a case study to thoroughly investigate cyberloafing that is linked to the cultural aspects of a country or the organisational work culture, which undoubtedly varies across different countries. Additionally, the theories utilised as sources might still be examined from the standpoint of several scientific disciplines. For instance, we could conduct research that draws on multidisciplinary knowledge.

In addition to the theoretical aspects, the practical application and consequences of studying cyberloafing are expected to offer insight into the policies of corporations or organizations about the regulation of employee conduct, which may have positive or negative effects. Finally, two further suggestions for future research emerged from jointly considering the cyberloafing literature. First, to comprehend the phenomenon of cyberloafing more fully in the AI era, which offers a variety of chances for job ease, it is required to consider it using research with a qualitative method approach. The goal is to determine whether AI impacts employees' cyberloafing behaviour. Second, several countries apply Internet regulatory policies to companies, but several articles have yet to explore the differences in regulations between developed and developing countries. In future research, it is necessary to look at work culture and country culture related to enforcing these internet rules.

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References

- Agarwal, U. A., & Avey, J. B. (2020). Abusive supervisors and employees who cyberloaf: Examining the roles of psychological capital and contract breach. *Internet Research*, 30(3), 789–809. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-05-2019-0208>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Akbulut, Y., Dönmez, O., & Dursun, Ö. Ö. (2017). Cyberloafing and social desirability bias among students and employees. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 72, 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.02.043>
- Andel, S., Pindek, S., & Arvan, M. L. (2022). Bored, angry, and overqualified? The high- and low-intensity pathways linking perceived overqualification to behavioural outcomes. *European Journal of Work and Organisational Psychology*, 31(1), 47–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2021.1919624>
- Demirtepe-Saygılı, D., & Metin-Orta, I. (2021). An Investigation of Cyberloafing in Relation to Coping Styles and Psychological Symptoms in an Educational Setting. *Psychological Reports*, 124(4), 1559–1587. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033294120950299>
- Durak, H. Y. (2020). Cyberloafing in Learning Environments Where Online Social Networking Sites Are Used as Learning Tools: Antecedents and Consequences. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(3), 539–569. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633119867766>
- Elrehail, H., Rehman, S. U., Chaudhry, N. I., & Alzghoul, A. (2021). Nexus among cyberloafing behaviour, job demands, and job resources: A mediated-moderated model. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(4), 4731–4749. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10496-1>
- Fakoor Saghih, A. M., & Nosrati, S. (2021). The antecedents of job embeddedness and their effects on cyberloafing among employees of public universities in eastern Iran. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 14(1), 77–93. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMEFM-11-2019-0489>
- Gökçearslan, Ş., Uluyol, Ç., & Şahin, S. (2018). Smartphone addiction, cyberloafing, stress, and social support among university students: A path analysis. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 91, 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.05.036>
- Hensel, P. G., & Kacprzak, A. (2020). Job Overload, Organizational Commitment, and Motivation as Antecedents of Cyberloafing: Evidence from Employee Monitoring Software. *European Management Review*, 17(4), 931–942. <https://doi.org/10.1111/emre.12407>
- Huma, Z., Hussain, S., Thurasamy, R., & Malik, M. I. (2017). Determinants of cyberloafing: A comparative study of a public and private sector organization. *Internet Research*, 27(1), 97–117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-12-2014-0317>
- Jandaghi, G., Alvani, S. M., Zarei Matin, H., & Fakheri Kozekanan, S. (2015). Cyberloafing Management in Organizations. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.22059/ijms.2015.52634>
- Kahn, R. L., Wolfe, D. M., Quinn, R. P., Snoek, J. D., & Rosenthal, R. A. (1964). *Organisational stress: Studies in role conflict and ambiguity*. (pp. xii, 470). John Wiley.
- Koay, K. Y. (2018). Workplace ostracism and cyberloafing: A moderated–mediation model. *Internet Research*, 28(4), 1122–1141. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-07-2017-0268>
- Koay, K. Y., Lim, V. K. G., Soh, P. C.-H., Ong, D. L. T., Ho, J. S. Y., & Lim, P. K. (2022). Abusive supervision and cyberloafing: A moderated moderation model of moral

- disengagement and negative reciprocity beliefs. *Information & Management*, 59(2), 103600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2022.103600>
- Lim, V. K. G. (2002). The IT way of loafing on the job: Cyberloafing, neutralising, and organisational justice. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 23(5), 675–694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.161>
- Lim, V. K. G., & Teo, T. S. H. (2024). Cyberloafing: A review and research agenda. *Applied Psychology*, 73(1), 441–484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12452>
- Mihelič, K. K., Lim, V. K. G., & Culiberg, B. (2023). Cyberloafing among Gen Z students: The role of norms, moral disengagement, multitasking self-efficacy, and psychological outcomes. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 38(2), 567–585. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-022-00617-w>
- Oosthuizen, A., Rabie, G. H., & De Beer, L. T. (2018). Investigating cyberloafing, organisational justice, work engagement, and organisational trust of South African retail and manufacturing employees. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v16i0.1001>
- Pindek, S., Krajcevska, A., & Spector, P. E. (2018). Cyberloafing as a coping mechanism: Dealing with workplace boredom. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 86, 147–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.04.040>
- Saritepeci, M. (2020). Predictors of cyberloafing among high school students: Unauthorised access to school network, metacognitive awareness, and smartphone addiction. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(3), 2201–2219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-10042-0>
- Wahyudi, L. (2025). *Watase Uake: Research Collaboration Tools*. Watase UAKE. <https://www.watase.web.id>
- Wu, J., Mei, W., Liu, L., & Ugrin, J. C. (2020). The bright and dark sides of social cyberloafing: Effects on employee mental health in China. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.02.043>
- Zakrzewski, C. (2016, March 13). *The Key to Getting Workers to Stop Wasting Time Online*. The Wall Street Journal. www.wsj.com